

REPORT

**WP 4: Rationalization of Poultry
Genebanks Strategy**

**Case Study — Centre for Genetic
Resources, the Netherlands (CGN)**

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1 Introduction

Genebank strategies and prioritization of approaches can differ considerably among genebanks depending on their specific circumstances, objectives, technical possibilities, and other factors.

The Centre for Genetic resources, the Netherlands (CGN) at Wageningen University and Research (WUR) counts on genebank collections of chicken, ducks and geese, among other mammalian livestock species. Its objective is to safeguard genetic diversity between and within breeds, especially of endangered Dutch breeds and locally adapted breeds (Schoon and Sluis 2024). To this objective CGN looks for establishing core collections, i.e. the minimum set of genetic material (doses and single donors) necessary to restore a breed in case of extinction (Schoon and Sluis 2024).

This report presents an overview of the current genebank strategy of the Genetic Resources Center of the Netherlands (CGN) at Wageningen University and Research (WUR). It analyzes the strengths and limitations of the current approach, based solely on semen cryopreservation, and compares it with the possible integration of primordial germ cells (PGCs) or gonadal germ cells (GGCs). The report examines the economic and human resource implications of these strategies. In addition, it evaluates whether the incorporation of PGCs or GGCs could help the CGN better achieve its genetic conservation goals and improve the cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency of its avian genebank program.

2 Current Status of CGN Poultry Conservation

Like many other genebanks, the CGN bases its poultry conservation strategy on semen cryopreservation. This method is widespread due to its relative simplicity, cost-effectiveness and technical feasibility. Semen can be collected easily from poultry, diluted, frozen and stored in liquid nitrogen for long-term use, making it a practical option for preserving paternal genetic material (Woelders 2021). Furthermore, this method is compatible with field conditions and can be easily integrated into breeding programmes.

CGN holds semen samples from native Dutch breeds of chicken (31 breeds) duck (5 breeds) and goose (1 breed) (Schoon and Sluis 2024). The currently stored semen samples form part of the core genetic collections for each of these breeds. CGN has determined (Schoon and Sluis 2024) the size required of the core collections considering the inbreeding rate per generation (ΔF) and the effective population size (N_e) in three different conservation scenarios: safe, compromised and risky (Table 1).

Table 1. CGN conservation scenarios based on inbreeding rate and effective population size.

	Scenario	ΔF	Ne
1	Safe (S)	0.5%,	100
2	Compromised (C)	0.67%,	74
3	Risky (R):	1%	50

ΔF , inbreeding rate per generation; Ne, effective population size. Adapted from Schoon and Sluis 2024.

The comparison between the genetic material required for effective restoration of the breeds and the current stocks in the CGN genebank indicated that, with the exception of the Hollands Hoen chicken and the Noord-Hollandse Krombekeend duck, none of the conserved poultry breeds has sufficient material to allow for recovery (Figure 1). Furthermore, these two breeds only meet the minimum thresholds in the ‘risky’ conservation scenario (effective population size $Ne = 50$; inbreeding rate $\Delta F = 1\%$), which represents the least stringent standard for genetic restoration (Table 1).

In addition, although the CGN has numerous semen samples available, the ability of frozen semen alone to guarantee the restoration of any breed is limited due to the variable and often low fertility rates they produce, especially native breeds (Thelie et al. 2019; Woelders 2021; Sun et al. 2022; Zong et al. 2023). This technical limitation significantly reduces the effectiveness of semen-based conservation strategies for avian species.

Figure 1. Overview of the percentages Dutch breeds within an animal species with insufficient or sufficient material available for the three reconstruction scenarios (Safe, Compromised, Risky or Insufficient for all scenarios) (Schoon and Sluis 2024).

3 Strategies integrating PGCs or GGCs

Despite semen preservation offers operational advantages (Table 2), it also has biological limitations, such as the inability to preserve the maternal and mitochondrial genomes.

Table 2. Comparison of Key Parameters in Semen vs. PGC-Based Conservation Strategies

Aspect	Semen		PGC
Equipment cost	(+) Low to moderate (cryotanks, basic lab)	(-) High (cell culture lab, CO ₂ incubator, micromanipulation)	
Consumables & reagents	(+) Low (extenders, straws, LN2)	(-) High (media, growth factors, antibodies, LN2)	
Human resources required	(+) Low to moderate (trained technicians)	(-) High (specialized cell culture personnel)	
Technical complexity	(+) Low (standardized AI protocols)	(-) High (species-specific protocols, microinjection)	
Time to restore a breed	(-) Long (5–6 generations)	(+) Short (3 generations)	
Preservation of male and female lines	(-) Only paternal line preserved	(+) Both male and female lines preserved	
Fertility and success rate	(-) Moderate to low in native breeds	(+) Variable, but high potential with optimized lines	

PGC= primordial germ cells, GGC= gonadal germ cells, LN2= liquid nitrogen

A promising novel strategy to preserve germplasm of male and female germplasm is the cryopreservation of Primordial Germ Cells (PGCs) (Whyte et al. 2015; Woodcock et al. 2019; Ichikawa and McGrew 2024). PGCs are the precursor cells in embryos responsible for the formation of gonads and the future production of sperm and ova in adults. Primordial Germ Cells (PGCs) can be isolated from 2.5-day-old embryos, typically yielding approximately 50–150 cells per embryo. These cells can be expanded in vitro to reach significantly higher numbers (e.g., up to 100,000 cells; Hu et al., 2022), and subsequently cryopreserved for long-term storage (Figure 2a). This approach enables the preservation of the female genome, which is an essential complement to sperm-based conservation methods, and allows for the complete recovery of the genome upon reconstitution.

Cryopreserved PGCs (from a female embryo) can be injected into a recipient female embryo (~3000 PGCs/embryo), and will colonise the gonads of the recipient. When the recipient embryo becomes an adult hen, ovaries can produce donor genotype oocytes (Hu et al. 2022) and, after insemination with cryopreserved semen of the same donor breed, the hen will produce pure offspring of the donor breed and crossbreed offspring (Figure 2a). This strategy has a demonstrated success (Whyte et al. 2015; Woodcock et al. 2019), and is much more cost-efficient than the gene banking of only semen.

Furthermore, the use of sterile recipient embryos during reintroduction avoids the generation of chimeric individuals and ensures the production of genetically pure offspring in the first generation (Woodcock et al. 2019).

However, despite these significant advantages, the technology also presents several limitations and operational challenges that must be carefully considered for its large-scale implementation (Table 2).

Another approach has recently been tested (Hu et al. 2022; 2024), cryopreservation of female gonads from 10 days-old embryos (Figure 2b) can be an efficient alternative for biobanking chicken female material. After thawing the gonads, over 10 000 gonadal germs cells (GGCs) can be isolated from them (Hu et al. 2022; 2024), much more than the 50-150 PGCs obtained from early embryos. The GGCs can be injected directly into 2.5 days-old embryos and migrate to the host gonad to colonize it. This strategy is economically feasible and is technically simple. However, the success of this strategy requires development of a validated freezing medium and protocol for the gonads that allows functional post-thaw recovery of the GGCs, and their ability to colonize the host embryonic gonad.

Figure 2. Breed restoration by cryopreservation of PGCs or embryo gonads and semen. Adapted from Woodcock et al 2019 and Hu et al 2022.

Although PGC-based conservation involves a higher initial investment in equipment compared to semen preservation (Table 3), CGN benefits from having an existing embryo laboratory. By sharing facilities, the additional investment needed for PGCs cryopreservation can be substantially reduced (Table 3).

The evaluation of various poultry cryopreservation strategies — including semen and PGC cryopreservation — considering operational costs, generations needed, time to breed recovery, and technical complexity, can provide valuable insights to assess whether the implementation of PGC or GGC technologies at CGN would be justified and strategically beneficial.

Table 3. Equipment costs for semen and PGCs cryopreservation

	Category	Possible Suppliers	Min Cost (EUR)	Max Cost (EUR)
Semen Only	Liquid nitrogen cryotanks	MVE Biological, Worthington	2790	6510
	Spectrophotometer / CASA system	Hamilton Thorne, IMV Technologies	10000	40000
	Low-speed centrifuge	Eppendorf, Hettich	930	2325
	Basic optical microscope	Olympus, Leica	465	1395
	Water bath	Grant Instruments, Julabo	279	744
	Insemination kit	IMV Technologies, Minitube	465	930
	Insemination training course	Minitube, Genex Cooperative	465	930
	Biosafety equipment	Thermo Fisher, 3M	465	1116
	Total		15859	53950
PGCs	Laminar flow hood	Thermo Fisher, Esco, Baker	5580	9300
	CO ₂ incubator	Panasonic, Binder, Memmert	4650	7440
	Inverted microscope	Olympus, Nikon, Leica	9300	18600
	Refrigerated centrifuge	Eppendorf, Thermo Fisher	2790	5580
	Programmable freezer	Planer, CryoMed	7440	11160
	Cryotanks for cells	MVE Biological, Worthington	2790	5580
	Specialized PGC training	STEMCELL, academic institutions	2325	4185
	Ethics & documentation	Institutional bioethics bodies	930	1116
	Egg incubator	Petersime, Brinsea, Rcom	500	2000
	Total		36305	64961
PGCs, using embryo lab	Specialized PGC training	STEMCELL, academic institutions	2325	4185
	Ethics & documentation	Institutional bioethics bodies	930	1116
	Egg incubator	Petersime, Brinsea, Rcom	500	2000
	Total		3755	7301

3.1 Conservation and Recovery Strategies — Cost Analysis

An economic assessment of various poultry conservation and restoration strategies is presented in Table 4. The strategies compared include semen cryopreservation (Strategy 1), using the existing cryopreservation facilities at CGN, and PGC cryopreservation (Strategies 2–5), utilizing the current embryo laboratory infrastructure.

Regarding PGC-based approaches, two strategies involve the cryopreservation of female and male PGCs followed by injection into either sterile (Strategy 2) or fertile (Strategy 3) embryos. Two additional combined strategies (Strategies 4 and 5) integrate semen cryopreservation with the cryopreservation of female PGCs injected into either sterile (Strategy 4) or fertile (Strategy 5) embryos. The assessment evaluates initial investment costs, the cost of cryopreserving

germplasm from 100 animals (safe scenario, $N_e = 100$), and the cost of breed restoration. Detailed information on the calculation methods used for each column can be found in Appendix 1, Tables 2A-5A.

Table 4. Total costs for conservation and breed restoration strategies

Strategy	Initial Investment ¹ (EUR)	Operational costs for conservation of 100 Animals ²	Breed Restoration ²	Total Costs
1 Semen Only	-	7100	69400	76500
2 PGCs ♀ + ♂ (sterile embryos)	7301	85280	15320	107901
3 PGCs ♀ + ♂ (fertile embryos)	7301	85280	72320	164901
4 Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile embryos)	7301	46190	30400	83891
5 Semen + PGCs ♀ (fertile embryos)	7301	46190	81400	134891

¹See Table 3 for additional details. ²See Appendix 1, Tables 1A - 4A for additional details. ³ See Appendix 1 Table 5A for additional details.

Given that CGN has access to facilities for both semen and embryo cryopreservation, the initial investment for implementing PGCs cryopreservation in the current facilities is much lower compared to a new PGCs lab. Regarding the strategies each one offers a distinct combination of biological processes, logistical considerations, and anticipated outcomes as described below

Semen only is the most cost-effective strategy, with the lowest total cost (€76,500) and no initial investment required. However, this method does not preserve the female genome and may not be suitable for comprehensive conservation goals.

PGCs ♀ + ♂ strategies are significantly more expensive. The total cost for using sterile embryos is €107,901, while the use of fertile embryos increases the total cost to €164,901, making it the most expensive option. The high costs are mainly driven by elevated breed restoration costs when using fertile embryos.

Combined Semen + PGCs ♀ strategies offer a more balanced cost profile. The use of sterile embryos results in a total cost of €83,891, which is both cost-effective and allows for complete genome recovery. The fertile embryo variant, however, raises the total cost to €134,891, again due to higher restoration costs.

The choice between sterile and fertile embryos has a substantial impact on total costs. In both PGCs-only and combined strategies, sterile embryos consistently result in lower breed restoration costs and overall lower total costs.

3.2 Conservation and Recovery Strategies — Generations Needed and Time Analysis

Table 5 summarizes the estimated number of generations and total time required to restore a chicken breed using different conservation and restoration strategies. A reproductive cycle of 8–10 months per generation is assumed. The analysis of the 5 strategies are explained below.

Table 5. Breed Restoration Strategies – Estimated Generations and Time Required

Strategy	Estimated Generations	Time (Years)
1 Semen Only	7 generations (backcrossing required)	~5–6 years
2 PGCs ♀ + ♂ (sterile embryos)	2–3 generations (F1 fertile + population expansion)	~2–3 years
3 PGCs ♀ + ♂ (fertile embryos)	3–4 generations (to fully stabilize genetic background)	~3–4 years
4 Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile embryos)	2–3 generations (PGCs generate F1 fertile individuals + semen complements genetic diversity)	~2–3 years
5 Semen + PGCs ♀ (fertile embryos)	2–3 generations (synergistic approach: PGCs and semen)	~2–3 years

1. Semen Only

In this strategy, frozen semen is used to inseminate recipient hens. Since no original breed females are available, multiple rounds of crossing (known as backcrossing) are needed to progressively recover the full genetic background of the original breed. This process typically requires around 7 generations, with each generation taking approximately 8–10 months (6 ideally), resulting in a total restoration time of about 5–6 years.

2. PGCs ♀ + ♂ injected in sterile embryos

In this strategy, both female and male Primordial Germ Cells (PGCs) are injected into sterile embryos. These embryos produce only offspring derived from the donor breed. This allows for very fast and efficient breed recovery in just 2–3 generations (about 2–3 years), with excellent genetic accuracy.

3. PGCs ♀ and ♂ injected in fertile embryos

This approach also uses PGCs, but they are injected into fertile embryos that can contribute some of their own genetic material. As a result, more generations (3–4) are needed to fully recover the donor breed's genetic profile, typically taking 3–4 years.

4. Semen + PGCs ♀ (injected in sterile embryos)

This combined method uses frozen semen together with female PGCs injected into sterile embryos. It offers fast and effective breed recovery in 2–3 generations (2–3 years) while improving genetic diversity by combining both semen and PGC-derived contributions. It is more robust than using a single method.

5. Semen + PGCs ♀ (injected in sterile embryos)

Similar to the previous method, but using fertile embryos. The combined use of frozen semen and PGCs allows for fast breed restoration in 2–3 generations (2–3 years). However, it requires more careful management because fertile embryos can contribute their own genetics, which must be balanced during the recovery process.

In summary, while all strategies can ultimately achieve breed restoration, they differ greatly in the time required and in technical complexity. PGC-based and combined approaches offer the fastest results, but they may present practical bottlenecks related to PGC handling and germline competence. In contrast, the “Semen” strategy is more time-consuming but relies on more established techniques. Selecting the most appropriate strategy depends on available resources, technical capabilities, and conservation goals.

3.3 Conservation and Recovery Strategies — Complexity

The technical complexity of each strategy was evaluated based on several factors: the number of required biological processes, the use of genetically modified or sterile lines, the need for advanced laboratory techniques, and the degree of integration between laboratory and field procedures. A scale from 1 to 5 was used to assess the complexity of the strategies analysed to date. The criteria used to assign a score are described in Table 6.

Table 6. Criteria for Technical Complexity (1–5)

Score	Main Requirements
1	Basic animal management; natural mating only; no AI, cryopreservation, or embryo manipulation.
2	AI with frozen/thawed semen; no embryo manipulation; basic lab (semen handling, quality control) and routine animal management.
3	PGC collection and injection into fertile eggs; advanced embryo handling; no sterile recipients or gene editing; moderate lab-field coordination.
4	PGC injection + sterile recipients (gene-edited or validated); advanced lab (CRISPR, PGC handling); higher lab-field integration; AI optional.
5	Full integration: PGC injection + sterile recipients + AI + advanced breeding management; maximum coordination across lab and field operations.

Abbreviations: AI= artificial insemination

Table 7 shows the complexity score assigned to each strategy. The complexity assessment highlights clear differences among the evaluated conservation strategies. Semen Only is the least complex approach (score 2), requiring no embryo manipulation and relying on well-established artificial insemination and semen handling techniques.

In contrast, strategies involving PGCs generally exhibit higher complexity (scores 4–5), due to the need for PGC injection, management of sterile or advanced breeding lines, and the integration of laboratory and field procedures. The combined Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile embryos) strategy stands

out as the most complex (score 5), reflecting the dual requirements of managing **both semen cryopreservation and PGC-based recovery processes**, alongside the use of gene-edited or sterile lines.

Overall, strategies incorporating PGCs with fertile embryos present a slightly lower complexity (score 4), as they avoid the need for sterile line management or gene editing but still require substantial technical coordination. These findings underscore the importance of considering technical feasibility and available infrastructure when selecting an optimal conservation strategy.

Table 7. Complexity assessment of each conservation strategy

Strategy	Complexity (1-5)	Justification
1 Semen Only	2	AI + semen freezing/thawing + animal management. No embryo manipulation required
2 PGCs ♀ + ♂ (sterile embryos)	4	Includes PGC injection + use of sterile lines (requires gene editing or maintenance of sterile lines). Advanced line management.
3 PGCs ♀ + ♂ (fertile embryos)	4	If using PGCs in fertile eggs, there is no gene editing or sterile lines involved → the manipulation is more "biological", not genetic engineering but requires housing + controlled breeding (therefore 4 is better than 3)
4 Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile embryos)	5	Sterile online PGCs + housing + AI + double process (semen + PGC). High level of coordination between laboratory and field.
5 Semen + PGCs ♀ (fertile embryos)	4	Similar to strategy 3, but adds AI. However, it does not involve editing or sterile lines → does not justify 5

Abbreviations: AI= artificial insemination

3.4 Using Gonadal Germ Cells to Optimize the Cost of PGC Strategies

Recent research has demonstrated that Gonadal Germ Cells (GGCs), harvested directly from the gonads of embryonic poultry (~day 9-10), can be cryopreserved and subsequently used to restore genetic lines with high germline transmission efficiency (Figure 2) (Hu et al. 2022).

This approach offers a practical alternative to the more technically demanding and costly in vitro culture of circulating PGCs, by simplifying the isolation process and eliminating the need for extended cell expansion. The natural abundance of GGCs in embryonic gonads further increases collection efficiency and reduces operational costs.

Integrating this method into the "Semen + ♀ PGCs (sterile)" strategy could significantly enhance its cost-effectiveness and feasibility, particularly for germplasm banks operating under resource constraints. By replacing cultured PGCs with directly cryopreserved GGCs, the strategy would maintain its advantages in terms of rapid genetic recovery and genetic stability, while lowering the barriers to large-scale implementation.

Therefore, adopting GGC-based approaches represents a promising avenue to make the “Semen + ♀ PGCs (sterile)” strategy even more accessible and sustainable for poultry genetic conservation programs.

4 Determining the best strategy for CGN

This section presents an integrated assessment of the proposed strategies for poultry conservation and breed recovery, taking into account total cost, time to restore a viable population, number of generations required, and technical complexity (Figure 3). The aim is to support the identification of the most cost-effective and operationally feasible approach for long-term germplasm conservation.

The assessment compared semen preservation, primordial germ cells (PGCs), and combined approaches to identify the strategy that offers the best balance between genetic stability and practical implementation.

Figure 3. Comparative analysis of conservation strategies for poultry breeds. The figure compares semen, PGCs, and combined strategies to determine the optimal approach for achieving genetic stability and operational feasibility. Abbreviations: S= semen, se= sterile embryos, fe= fertile embryos.

The comparative analysis of different conservation and recovery strategies for poultry breeds, as illustrated in the figure, highlights several important trade-offs between total cost, time required to restore a breed, and technical complexity.

1. Cost

The "Semen" strategy represents the most cost-effective option (€76.5k), whereas the "PGCs (fe)" approach incurs the highest cost (€164.9k). Combined strategies such as "Semen + PGCs (se)" offer a favourable balance, achieving relatively low cost (€83.9k) while ensuring effective outcomes.

2. Time to Restore

Strategies that incorporate PGCs (both sterile and fertile) and combined approaches demonstrate significantly shorter restoration times (3 years), in contrast to the "Semen" strategy, which requires up to 6 years. This highlights the importance of selecting advanced methods for breeds at high risk or where rapid recovery is essential.

3. Technical Complexity

Simpler strategies, such as "Semen," exhibit low technical complexity, making them easier to implement. However, this comes at the expense of extended recovery time and genetic stability. More sophisticated strategies involving PGCs demonstrate higher technical complexity (up to level 5), which must be considered in terms of institutional capacity and expertise.

The "Semen + PGCs ♀ (se)" strategy (semen + female PGCs injected in sterile embryos) emerges as one of the most balanced options, offering rapid breed recovery (3 years), acceptable cost, and high genetic quality, despite its high technical complexity. This trade-off is often justified when dealing with the conservation of high-value or critically endangered poultry breeds.

In contrast, while "Semen" is the least expensive and technically simplest option, it is suboptimal for urgent conservation needs due to its extended recovery period and greater number of generations required. The "PGCs (fe)" strategy (semen + ♀ PGCs injected in sterile embryos), despite its genetic advantages, presents cost and complexity challenges that may limit its practicality in resource-constrained settings.

The choice of strategy should therefore be guided by the specific priorities and resources of the germplasm bank—whether the aim is maximum speed, minimal complexity, or operation under strict budget constraints. For high-priority breeds requiring urgent recovery and genetic stability, combined approaches incorporating PGCs are strongly recommended.

5 Public Acceptance of PGC/GGC Technology

The use of PGC (Primordial Germ Cell) and GGC (Gonadal Germ Cell) technologies in genetic conservation and breed restoration is a promising but relatively novel approach. As with any advanced biotechnological intervention, its acceptance may vary across different types of stakeholders and the general public. However, the public perception of this technology will likely depend on several factors, including awareness of the technology, understanding of its purpose, perceived benefits, and ethical or cultural considerations. It is therefore important to assess the acceptance of this technology among different audiences.

In particular, the application of PGC and GGC technologies involves the sacrifice of embryos at early developmental stages, a practice that may trigger ethical sensitivities or concerns among certain segments of the public.

According to Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes, the protection of avian embryos applies only from the last third of their normal development. Embryos used for the isolation of PGCs (~2.5 days of development) and GGCs (~9–10 days of development) fall well before this protected period. Therefore, these procedures are not subject to the regulatory requirements for animal protection under this directive.

Nevertheless, despite being legally permissible, the use of early-stage avian embryos may raise ethical concerns or sensitivities among certain stakeholder groups. This highlights the importance of assessing public acceptance and ensuring transparency in the application of such technologies for poultry genetic conservation.

It is therefore essential to assess the acceptance of this technology across different audiences to ensure that its implementation is conducted in a socially responsible and transparent manner.

5.1 Survey on PGC/GGC Technology Acceptance

To assess the perception of different target groups regarding the adoption of PGCs/GGCs (Primordial Germ Cells / Gonadal Germ Cells) technology as a strategy for avian genetic preservation, a 7-question survey was conducted among the general public (including students), professionals working in conservation, private sector stakeholders, gene bank representatives, and a poultry breeders' association.

The invitation to participate in the survey was accompanied by an infographic explaining the technology. This approach helped raise awareness about the technology while ensuring that respondents had a basic understanding of it prior to answering the questions. The infographics, available in multiple languages, can be accessed at the following link:

The survey included the following seven questions:

1 Do you have previous knowledge of biotechnology applied to species conservation?

- a Yes, I have extensive knowledge.
- b I have some knowledge.
- c No, I am not familiar with it.

2 Which group do you belong to?

- a General audience
- b Professionals related to the topic
- c Private sector
- d Associations/Organizations
- e Gene banks
- f Other

3 Before this survey, did you know about PGC/GGC (cells contained in chick embryos that will transform into oocytes or spermatozoa) ?

- a Yes, I was already familiar with them.
- b I had heard about them but did not know much.
- c No, this is my first time learning about them.
- d I am not sure / I need more information.

4 Do you think PGC/GGC technology can be an effective tool for preserving chickens and other poultry, especially females?

- a Yes, I firmly believe in its effectiveness.
- b I think it could be useful, but I have some doubts.
- c I'm not sure / I need more information.
- d No, I don't think it's effective.

5 What do you consider to be the main benefits of applying PGC/GGC technology?

- a Biodiversity preservation
- b Genetic improvement (better breeds)
- c Protection of endangered species
- d Scientific advancement
- e Economic benefits
- f Other

6 What are your main concerns about the application of PGC/GGC technology?

- a Ethical implications
- b Regulatory issues
- c High cost
- d Social acceptance
- e I have no concerns
- f Other

7 If you had funds to invest, would you choose sperm cryopreservation or the preservation of hen's PGC/GGC?

- a Sperm Cryopreservation
- b Primordial Germ Cells (PGCs)/gonadal germ cells (GGCs) of hens
- c A and B
- d None of the above

The survey was available in the following links:

[Innovación en la conservación de las aves. ¡Las hembras también son importantes! - Midnight](#)
[Innovation in Bird Conservation. Females are important too! - Midnight](#)
[Innovation dans la conservation des oiseaux. Les femelles sont également importantes ! - Midnight](#)

5.2 Survey Results on PGC/GGC Technology Acceptance

This section reports the results from 369 questionnaires completed to assess how different kind of public perceive PGC/GGC technology. The findings provide valuable insights into awareness levels, perceived benefits, concerns, and investment priorities related to the use of PGC/GGC approaches in gene banks. (Details about the number of answers per question are shown in Appendix 2, Table 2.

1. Awareness and baseline knowledge of biotechnology and PGC/GGC.

A significant proportion of respondents (~35%) reported having some or extensive knowledge of biotechnology applied to species conservation. However, around 65% had little or no familiarity with PGC/GGC specifically prior to the survey. This highlights the need for further outreach and education on this technology.

2. Perceived effectiveness of PGC/GGC

Survey results indicate a strong positive attitude towards the effectiveness of PGC/GGC technology:

- 45% of respondents firmly believe in its effectiveness.
- 39% believe it could be useful but have some doubts.
- Only 2 respondents indicated that they do not believe it is effective.

This suggests high potential acceptance if the technology is well explained and demonstrated.

3. Perceived benefits

Respondents identified multiple key benefits of applying PGC/GGC technology:

- Biodiversity preservation (307 votes)
- Protection of endangered species (278 votes)
- Economic benefits (187 votes)

The community clearly sees the conservation value of PGC/GGC and appreciates its potential economic and scientific contributions.

4. Main concerns

The main concerns expressed were:

- High cost (174 votes) — the most significant concern.
- Ethical implications (161 votes)
- Regulatory issues (115 votes)
- Social acceptance (80 votes)

Cost is the most immediate concern. Addressing cost-efficiency and providing clear ethical and regulatory frameworks will be essential for broad acceptance.

5. Stakeholder composition

The survey captured a broad audience:

- General audience: 233 respondents
- Professionals related to the topic: 68
- Additional representation from gene banks, private sector, and organisations: 33
- Other: 19
- Unknown: 16

The results reflect a good level of interest across diverse stakeholder groups.

6. Investment priorities: Sperm vs. PGC/GGC cryopreservation

Survey results demonstrate a strong preference for a combined investment approach. A majority of respondents (61%) indicated that they would choose to invest in both sperm and PGC/GGC cryopreservation, recognising the complementary value of these two technologies. Furthermore, 25% of respondents expressed a preference for investing specifically in PGC/GGC preservation, underscoring the perceived importance of safeguarding female genetic material.

By contrast, only 8% of respondents would invest solely in sperm cryopreservation, suggesting a broad understanding of the limitations of sperm-only strategies in avian species conservation. A small proportion (6%) selected “None of the above,” indicating minimal rejection or indifference towards cryopreservation as a whole.

Overall, these findings clearly support the inclusion of PGC/GGC cryopreservation within avian gene bank strategies and justify the allocation of resources to this area.

6 Conclusions and recommendations for CGN conservation strategy.

This section summarizes the key conclusions and actionable recommendations for CGN based on the comparative analysis of conservation strategies and the insights gathered from the stakeholder survey. These findings aim to guide decision-making and support the responsible adoption of PGC/GGC technologies in avian germplasm conservation.

6.1 Conclusions

The comparative analysis of conservation strategies highlights that combined approaches incorporating PGCs, particularly the Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile) strategy, offer a highly effective balance between rapid recovery (3 years), acceptable cost, and high genetic quality. Despite its technical complexity, this trade-off is justified when preserving high-value or critically endangered poultry breeds.

Conversely, the Semen strategy, while the least expensive and simplest to implement, is not suitable for urgent conservation needs due to its extended recovery time and higher number of required generations. Strategies based solely on PGCs (fertile), while genetically advantageous, pose cost and complexity challenges that may limit their practical application, especially in resource-constrained contexts.

Survey results further confirm broad support among stakeholders for the adoption of combined PGCs/sperm strategies in avian germplasm conservation. Respondents recognize the advantages of such approaches, although cost remains the primary concern. The survey also underscores the importance of increasing awareness, fostering ethical clarity, and establishing regulatory frameworks to facilitate the acceptance and responsible use of PGC/GGC technologies.

6.2 Recommendations

- **Prioritize combined PGC + sperm strategies:** For high-priority or endangered poultry breeds, germplasm banks should prioritize combined PGC + sperm approaches, with Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile) currently representing the most balanced option.
- **Develop cost-efficient protocols:** Given that cost is perceived as a key barrier, efforts should focus on improving the efficiency of PGC protocols as for example the use of GGCs instead of PGC and developing transparent cost models to support long-term sustainability.
- **Promote awareness and capacity building:** To ensure broader acceptance and informed adoption, germplasm banks should invest in awareness campaigns, targeted education, and

training on PGC/GGC technologies for stakeholders, including private sector actors and conservation professionals.

- Establish clear ethical and regulatory frameworks: Clear guidelines and regulatory frameworks should be developed in collaboration with relevant authorities to address ethical considerations and ensure responsible use of PGC/GGC technologies in poultry conservation.
- Foster ongoing dialogue and transparency: Active dialogue, transparent reporting, and open communication regarding the benefits and limitations of PGC/GGC technologies will be essential to build trust among stakeholders and the broader public, thereby facilitating their responsible and widespread adoption.

These recommendations aim to support germplasm banks in making informed, strategic decisions regarding the integration of PGC/GGC technologies into their conservation programs, ensuring both scientific rigor and broad stakeholder engagement.

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APPENDIX 1

Table 1A. Conservation costs for Semen , PGCs, and Combined Strategy (50 Semen + 50 PGCs)

Item	Cost per animal (EUR)	Cost for 100 animals		
		Semen ³ (EUR)	PGCs (♂ + ♀) ³ (EUR)	50 Semen + 50 ♀ PGCs ³ (EUR)
Semen diluent (per male)	5	500	-	250
Straws (5 per male)	5	500	-	250
Nitrogen storage (1 yr)	10	1000	1000	1000
Basic technician (2h @ €20)	40	4000	-	2000
PGC media (8 weeks)	251.6	-	25160	12580
Antibodies / supplements	120	-	12000	6000
Plasticware (48-well plates, filters)	7	-	700	350
PGC technician (16.3h @ €25) ¹	408	-	40800	20400
PGC+Semen shared handling & screening	50	-	5000	2500
StemCell Banker (for PGC cryopreservation)	3	-	300	150
CPA (for semen cryopreservation)	5	500	-	250
Collection and transport of semen to the lab ²	6	600	-	300
Purchase of eggs (for PGC collection)	0.8	-	240	120
Transport of eggs (PGC collection)	80	-	80	40
TOTAL		7100	85280	46190

Note: StemCell Banker cost based on €150 per 100 mL. Uses ~1 mL per line (we consider 2 mL), thus €3 per animal. ¹Details in Table 2A. ²Details in Table 3A. ³Details in Table 4A.

Table 2A. Estimated Technical Labour Cost for PGC Maintenance and Handling

Activity	Estimated Technical Time (h)	Technical Cost (€)
Medium change (every 3rd day over 8 weeks)	6.3 × €25 / h	157.5
Sex determination of PGCs	2 × €25 / h	50
Injection of PGCs into recipient embryo	2 × €25 / h	50
Identity analysis of PGCs	3 × €25 / h	75
Isolation and initial seeding of PGCs	3 × €25 / h	75
Total	16.3 × €25 / h	407.5

Table 3A. Detailed Cost Calculation for Collection and Transport of Semen

Concept	Value
Outbound driving time	1 h
Return driving time	1 h
Collection and conditioning	1 h
TOTAL time per collection	3 h
Basic technician hourly rate (€ / h)	€20 / h
Total cost per collection	3 h × €20 / h = €60
Animals transported per trip	10 animals
Cost per animal	€60 / 10 = €6 / animal
Cost for 100 animals	€6 × 100 = €600

Table 4A. Detailed incremental cost per animal for cryopreserving Semen, PGCs, or both (Combined)

Item	Strategy	Calculation Method	Possible suppliers
Semen diluent (per male)	Semen	Includes semen extender (€1–2), antibiotics and processing consumables (~€3–4) → €5 per male	IMV Technologies, Minitube
Straws (5 per male)	Semen	€5 per male × number of males (5 straws @ €1 each)	IMV Technologies, Agtech Inc.
Nitrogen storage (1 yr)	All	Shared tank estimated at €1000/year storing ~100 animals → €10 per animal	Linde Gas, Air Liquide, Praxair
Basic technician (2h @ €20)	Semen, Combined	2 hours @ €20/hr = €40; assumed same handling in combined	General lab staff / internal
PGC media (8 weeks)	PGCs, Combined	€262.1 per 500 mL; each animal uses 240 mL (based on 8-week usage) → ~€251.6	Calculated according to (Woodcock et al. 2019)
Antibodies / supplements	PGCs, Combined	Cell markers and growth factors ~€60 per animal	Abcam, Thermo Fisher
Plasticware (48-well plates, filters)	PGCs, Combined	1 × 48-well plate + disposables = €3.50 per animal → €7	Corning, Eppendorf
PGC technician (16.5h @ €25) ¹	PGCs, Combined	16.3 hours @ €25/hr × = €408	STEMCELL Technologies, academic institutions
PGC+Semen shared handling & screening	Combined	Additional logistics (e.g., PCR, sorting) ~€50	Labgenomics, Eurofins Genomics
StemCell Banker (for PGC cryopreservation)	PGCs, Combined	€150/100 mL; 2 mL per animal → €3	AMSBIO, StemCell Technologies
CPA (for semen cryopreservation)	Semen, Combined	Used at ~6%-8%; ~€5 per dose	Sigma-Aldrich, Thermo Fisher
Collection and transport of semen to the lab ²	Semen	€6 per animal (collection + transport)	Institutional cost/logistics cost

Abbreviations: CPA= cryoprotectant; PGCs primordial germ cells. ^{1,2}For detailed calculation methods see Table 2A and 3A , respectively.

Table 5A. Detailed Cost Breakdown of Breed Restoration Strategies

Strategy	Component	Calculation Formula	Units	Unit Cost (EUR)	Sub-total Cost (EUR)
Semen Only	Retro-crossing (7 gens)	7 gens × (€2000 breeding + €6000 animal care/gen)	7	8000	56000
	Thawing & preparation of frozen semen	100 semen thawings × €50	100	50	5000
	Field labor & insemination	6 AI/gen × 7 gens × €200	42	200	8400
	Total cost				69400
PGCs ♀ + ♂ (sterile embryos)	Gene-edited recipient embryos	CRISPR validation + 100 sterile embryos @ €50	100	50	5000
	Injection & breeding (G0–G2, 1 year)	300 injections + housing + staff	1	10000	10000
	Purchase of recipient eggs (sterile)	300 eggs × €0.80	1	240	240
	Transport of recipient eggs (PGC injection)	4h × €20/h = €80 per batch	1	80	80
Total cost				15320	
PGCs ♀ + ♂ (fertile embryos)	Injection into fertile embryos	300 injections × €40 + 25% donor germline = ×4	1	48000	48000
	Housing & staff	4 years × €6000 per year	4	6000	24000
	Purchase of recipient eggs (fertile)	300 eggs × €0.80	1	240	240
	Transport of recipient eggs (PGC injection)	4h × €20/h = €80 per batch	1	80	80
Total cost				72320	
Semen + PGCs ♀ (sterile embryos)	Gene-edited recipient embryos	CRISPR validation + 100 sterile embryos @ €50	100	50	5000
	Injection & breeding (G0–G2, 1 year)	300 injections + housing + staff	1	10000	10000
	Purchase of recipient eggs (sterile)	300 eggs × €0.80	1	240	240
	Transport of recipient eggs (PGC injection)	4h × €20/h = €80 per batch	1	80	80
	Thawing & preparation of frozen semen	100 semen thawings × €50	100	50	5000
	Artificial insemination + selection	100 inseminations × €200 + 50 selected offspring	1	10000	10000
	Total cost				30400
Semen + PGCs ♀ (fertile embryos)	Injection into fertile embryos	300 injections × €40 + 25% donor germline = ×4	1	48000	48000
	Purchase of recipient eggs (fertile)	300 eggs × €0.80	1	240	240
	Transport of recipient eggs (PGC injection)	4h × €20/h = €80 per batch	1	80	80
	Thawing & preparation of frozen semen	100 semen thawings × €50	100	50	5000
	Insemination + selection	100 inseminations × €200 + 50 selected offspring	1	10000	10000
	Housing & staff	3 years × €6000 per year	3	6000	18000
Total cost				81400	

APPENDIX 2

1. Do you have previous knowledge of biotechnology applied to species conservation?

- Yes, I have extensive knowledge.
- I have some knowledge.
- No, I am not familiar with it.

2. Which group do you belong to?

- General audience
- Professionals related to the topic
- Private sector
- Associations/Organizations
- Gene banks
- Other

3. Before this survey, did you know about PGC/GGC (cells contained in chick embryos that will transform into oocytes or spermatozoa) ?

- Yes, I was already familiar with them.
- I had heard about them but did not know much.
- No, this is my first time learning about them.

4. Do you think PGC/GGC technology can be an effective tool for preserving chickens and other poultry, especially females?

- Yes, I firmly believe in its effectiveness.
- I think it could be useful, but I have some doubts.
- I'm not sure / I need more information.
- No, I don't think it's effective.

5. What do you consider to be the main benefits of applying PGC/GGC technology?

- Biodiversity preservation
- Genetic improvement (better breeds)
- Protection of endangered species
- Scientific advancement
- Economic benefits
- Other

6. What are your main concerns about the application of PGC/GGC technology?

- Ethical implications
- Regulatory issues
- High cost
- Social acceptance
- I have no concerns
- Other

7. If you had funds to invest, would you choose sperm cryopreservation or the preservation of hen's PGC/GGC?

- Sperm Cryopreservation
- Primordial Germ Cells (PGCs)/gonadal germ cells (GGCs) of hens
- A and B
- None of the above

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